

SECTION: OIL AND GAS FIRMS

DETERMINATION OF RISK FACTORS SIGNIFICANCE OF OIL AND GAS PRODUCTION ENTERPRISES' ACTIVITY

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ABSTRACT: The efficiency of risk management software depends on the quality of risk assessment at the stage of such system development. The number of potential variables (factors) in many risk management software applications is large. Another important aspect is that the scientists and engineers face to challenge which risk factors are significant or what the acceptable range of its values is at the initial stage of the risk controlling system development. The paper suggests a way to determine the significant specific risk factors of domestic oil and gas production enterprises' activity and to screen out the insignificant factors. In order to achieve these goals, the simulation analysis was conducted by the aid of 2-level full factorial experiment. Empirical data-processing operation was carried out through the instrumentality of mathematical statistics methods. It has been suggested to exclude (screen) at the stage of model construction eleven risk factors (of thirty-five ones identified), which impact on the financial and economical state of analyzed companies is insignificant (less than 5%).

JEL CLASSIFICATIONS: C99, G32, L71

KEYWORDS: Risk, risk factors, factor screening, 2^k full factorial experiment, oil and gas production enterprises

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1. Introduction

Business environment complications of oil and gas production enterprises against the background of world structural changes and increased costs of production of hydrocarbons lead to the need for risk controlling system implementation by such enterprises.

The efficiency of risk management software depends on the quality of risk assessment at the stage of such system development. The number of potential variables (factors) in many risk management software applications is large. Another important aspect is that the scientists and engineers face to challenge which risk factors are significant or what the acceptable range of its values is at the initial stage of the risk controlling system development.

The procedure of selection (screening) of factors which insignificantly affect the financial and economical state of the company is applied to reduce the number of factors analyzed by the risk controlling system. In order to enhance the research in this area, the project team has (based on two indices, namely probability of risk event and the degree of risk impact on the resultant value) to rank factors by the value of the risk, generated by them, and to exclude insignificant factors. This selection of factors allows focusing on the improvement of the process of management of risks, occurrence of which is caused by the significant risk factors only.

2. Statement of the research problem

In Ukraine, the application of internationally developed methodical approaches to the determination of the risk level by oil and gas companies is considerably complicated; it sometimes seems to be impossible due to the lack of information. The lack of complex experimental studies of specific risks, typical for domestic oil and gas enterprises, has caused us to perform the agreed expert assessment of its risk factors. For each risk factor of certain groups of risks, typical for by oil and gas companies, the experts have given the values for the probability of risk events and determined the degree of impact of risk factors (by each risk group) on the financial and economical state of oil and gas companies (Gryniuk, 2016a). Taking into account the significant amount of factors identified, we consider it necessary to identify and exclude those factors which have an insignificant impact on the financial and economical state of the companies. The main task of mathematical modeling of the object, in relation to which the factor screening is being carried out, is to select the significant factors and to eliminate the insignificant ones, using special methods, with a high degree of confidence of obtained results upon a minimum number of experiments. There are a lot of approaches to the screening of insignificant factors or its bad values in the mathematical statistics perspective. According to Wen Li (2015), there are different statistical methods available for factor screening, such as one-factor-at-a-time method, Taguchi's method, application of full factorial experiment design, fractional factorial experiment design, as well as Plackett-Burman designs. The following designs are also often used for screening: 1) 2-level full and fractional factorial designs; 2) Plackett-Burman fractional factorial design; 3) general full factorial design (with more than two levels of variation) (Minitab 17 Support, 2016). Insignificant risk factors will be eliminated based on the performance of 2^k full factorial design.

The aim of the research is to determine significant specific risk factors of domestic oil and gas production enterprises' activity and to screen out the insignificant factors using 2^k full factorial design.

3. Literature review

Nowadays, there are many domestic and foreign scientists' academic papers, dedicated to the topics of identification and assessment of the risk of business enterprises. The considerable contribution to the study of identification of factors of individual groups of risks (like ecological or geological risk factors), typical for the activity if the oil and gas production enterprises, as well as to its assessment approaches, has been made by many scientists. The latest research results concerning

identification of risks, its analysis and assessment techniques that are used in the oil and gas industry have been obtained by Johnsen, Aas, & Qian (2012), Marhavilas, Koulouriotis, & Gemeni (2011), Andersen & Mostue (2012), AlKazimi & Grantham (2015), Skogdalen & Vinnem (2011), Shahriar, Sadiq, & Tesfamariam (2012).

Risk identification is an initial stage of designing of the risk management system. Johnsen, Aas, & Qian (2012) have characterized the major accidents, threats, and defences in the perspective of Man-Technology-Organization (MTO) in oil and gas sector in their research paper. Examples of some major accidents in oil and gas industry from 1980 have been listed from the area's perspective (offshore drilling, process plants, and transport). Johnsen et al. (2012) also have suggested a set of "best practices" to mitigate the risks, explored with success in Norway.

Methodological approaches to risk assessment are listed in the significant amount of academic papers. The risk analysis and evaluation techniques are classified into three main categories: the qualitative, the quantitative, and the hybrid methods (qualitative, quantitative, semi-quantitative) (Marhavilas, Koulouriotis, & Gemeni, 2011). Marhavilas et al. (2011) have represented the classification of the main risk analysis and assessment methodologies, which have been analyzed in detail and can be used for assessment of risks of oil and gas production enterprises' activity. Andersen & Mostue (2012) have represented the overview of risk analytical methods for risk analysis and have performed the survey of the use of risk analysis in the Norwegian oil and gas industry. Common risk assessment tools used in the petroleum industry also have been described and analyzed by AlKazimi & Grantham (2015).

The analysis and assessment of risk factors of a particular group of risks of oil and gas industry occurs in academic papers more often than complex analysis of risks. Skogdalen & Vinnem (2011) have investigated human and organizational factors as the potential cause of failure in oil and gas industry. There are also many articles focused on risk analysis of the failure of equipment in oil and gas industry (drilling equipment, production, and transport equipment, and so on). Shahriar, Sadiq, & Tesfamariam (2012) have provided the complex experimental study of various risk factors associated with pipelines failures and proposed framework for risk analysis under uncertainty.

4. Methodology

4.1. Risk analysis

There are three main categories (classes) of risk analysis and assessment techniques: the qualitative, the quantitative and hybrid techniques (qualitative-quantitative, semi-quantitative).

The lack of reliable information, statistical data with reference to which we could assess the risk level of domestic oil and gas extraction enterprises' activity, and the lack of complex studies of specific risks of such companies determined the need for the expert survey. At the initial stage of our research, we had identified groups of the risk of domestic oil and gas extraction enterprises' activity, risk factors of each group and developed the research questionnaire (checklist) to conduct a qualitative risk analysis. Each risk factor of the certain group of risk was given by experts the values of probability of risk events; the experts determined the degree of impact of risk factors (by each risk group) on the financial and economical state of the observed companies (severity of risk factor).

The following step of our research is to conduct a risk assessment with the use of quantitative techniques. According to Marhavilas, Koulouriotis, & Gemeni (2011), the "quantitative" methods are the most-frequently-used.

Quantitative risk analysis is generally conducted by measuring the risk as a product of the likelihood of the occurrence of any undesirable event and the consequence of the corresponding undesirable event (Shahriar et al., 2012).

According to the almost all methodological approaches for quantitative risk analysis, the measure of the risk (risk index) can be calculated on the basis of available data or experts' judgment as the product of the probability of occurrence of the risk factor (accident, error of the system) and the severity of associated harm. Quantitative risk analysis can be applied to many different fields, among them: engineering, medicine, chemistry, biology, agronomics, etc. and to any company or production process. Described risk assessment method is exact and easy-to-use. The choice of this method of risk assessment was determined due to the advantages of the method and output parameters of experts' judgment. The methodology adopted to the object of research is shown below.

Therefore, a probability of risk event is denoted by p_{ij} . The rank, assigned to each risk factor by experts, in terms of its impact on the financial and economical state of the analyzed companies, is denoted by n_{ij} , where i is a sequence number of the risk factor in the group ($i = 1...k$, k is the number of factors in the group (subgroup) of risk) and j is a consecutive number of the expert, who has provided two variables (probability of risk event and its consequence (rank)) for each factor of analyzed risk groups ($j = 1...m$, m is the number of experts). For analyzed risk factors of 1.2. subgroup ("Machinery breakdowns by the causes of its occurrence") of the production and technological risk factors, i is equal to six and j is equal to eight. The identified risk factors of oil and gas production enterprises' activity are represented in Table 1 (Appendix) (Gryniuk, 2016b). The probability of risk event by the groups (subgroup) of risk factors and its consequences (ranks, assigned by the experts) are listed in (Gryniuk, 2016a).

Specific risk magnitude (R_{ij}) is the multiplication of the probability of risk factor event (p_{ij}) by its rank (n_{ij}). Furthermore, the sum of the probability of occurrence of all risk factors of the group (subgroup) is equal to one. The value of each risk factor is ranked by the degree of risk factor impact in the total value of risk of the group (subgroup) and is normalized, i.e. each risk factor is assigned by certain rank (point) from 1 to k . For 6-factor risk group, 1 is a minimum point, assigned to the factor, and 6 is a maximum point, assigned to the factor. Thus, the risk magnitude of the analyzed factor (risk index) can be calculated using the following formula:

$$R_{ij} = p_{ij} \times n_{ij}, \tag{1}$$

Where, R_{ij} is risk magnitude, p_{ij} is probability of risk event and n_{ij} is the rank, assigned to risk factor by experts, its impact on the financial and economical state of the analyzed companies.

If no risk factors are identified, then a mark of zero is awarded. According to the expert estimates for the risk factors, included into 1.2 subgroup of technological and production risk factors, calculated R_{ij} values based on the data, presented in

(Gryniuk, 2016a), are listed in Table 2; the average value of i -risk factor has been calculated using the following formula:

$$R_{aver.i.} = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^m R_{ij}}{m}, \quad (2)$$

Where, $R_{aver.i.}$ is an average value of i -risk factor, $\sum_{j=1}^m R_{ij}$ is the sum of risk magnitude calculated according to the given expert estimation for each risk factor, m is the number of experts.

TABLE 2. DETERMINATION OF RISK MAGNITUDE FOR FACTORS ANALYZED WITHIN
 1.2 SUBGROUP OF PRODUCTION AND TECHNOLOGICAL RISK FACTORS

Rates	R_1			R_2			R_3			R_4			R_5			R_6		
	p_{1j}	n_{1j}	R_{1j}	p_{2j}	n_{2j}	R_{2j}	p_{3j}	n_{3j}	R_{3j}	p_{4j}	n_{4j}	R_{4j}	p_{5j}	n_{5j}	R_{5j}	p_{6j}	n_{6j}	R_{6j}
	0.37	6	2.22	0.06	2	0.12	0.15	4	0.6	0.25	5	1.25	0.04	1	0.04	0.13	3	0.39
	0.3	6	1.8	0.02	1	0.02	0.2	4	0.8	0.22	5	1.1	0.08	2	0.16	0.18	3	0.54
	0.2	4	0.8	0.1	3	0.3	0.28	5	1.4	0.36	6	2.16	0.02	1	0.02	0.04	2	0.08
	0.35	6	2.1	0.08	2	0.16	0.1	3	0.3	0.27	5	1.35	0.05	1	0.05	0.2	4	0.8
	0.28	5	1.4	0.03	1	0.03	0.14	4	0.56	0.4	6	2.4	0.04	2	0.08	0.11	3	0.33
	0.3	6	1.8	0.2	3	0.6	0.16	4	0.64	0.24	5	1.2	0.03	1	0.03	0.07	2	0.14
	0.24	5	1.2	0.09	2	0.18	0.36	6	2.16	0.15	4	0.6	0.06	1	0.06	0.1	3	0.3
	0.22	5	1.1	0.04	2	0.08	0.32	6	1.92	0.18	4	0.72	0.17	3	0.51	0.07	1	0.07
Total	x	x	12.42	x	x	1.49	x	x	8.38	x	X	10.78	x	x	0.95	X	x	2.65
$R_{aver.i.}$	1.55250			0.18625			1.04750			1.34750			0.11875			0.33125		
r_i	0.338696			0.040633			0.228525			0.293973			0.025907			0.072266		

Source: Own.

Due to the fact, that $\sum_{i=1}^n R_{aver.i.} > 1$, the partial values of certain risk magnitude (r_i) are estimated to simplify the following calculations. In this case $\sum_{i=1}^n (r_i) = 1$.

4.2. Screening experiment

To carry out the design of experiment, the risk assessment should be taken into function first. A structured, organized method for determining the relationship between factors affecting a process and the output of that process is known as "Design of Experiments".

When using factor-screening design, it is necessary to construct a planning matrix and to carry out the pilot experiment. After considering the results of the pilot experiment, the factors' impact on the investigated process can be determined. Due to the fact, that, at the present stage of experiment performance, the resources (financial, labor, time resources, etc.) are limited, it is critical to get the most relevant information during each experiment, being performed. A well-designed experiment can produce significantly more information, provide identification of key risk factors and assessment of its impact on the resultant value and often requires fewer runs of the simulation model as compared to the random or unplanned experiments.

In order to illustrate the ED (experimental design) concept, let's consider the performance of simulation experiment of possible risk situations at oil and gas production enterprises for the study of negative impact of q_i parameters (risk factors) - q_1, q_2, \dots, q_k ($i=1 \dots k$, where k is quantity of factors in risk groups) - on the output result of the model, namely on the financial and economic state of the companies (its loss rate). The parameters, being studied, have a low (minimum) value and a high (maximum) value. These values are known as levels. During the simplest simulation, used in this work, each factor has two levels - low and high ones. These experimental simulations belong to a group of designs known as 2^k factorial experiments (designs), where k is the number of parameters being studied (Quinao & Zarrouk, 2014). The full factorial design provides for the taking into account of all combinations of factors at levels studied, creating 2^k combinations of factorial design conditions and is (Walpole, Myers, Myers, & Ye, 2012).

The 2-level full factorial experiment is applied to divide risk factors into two parts: risk factors that have a significant impact on the financial and economical state of the observed enterprises and insignificant factors. During the screening experiment, the matrix of possible combinations of risk factors influencing the financial and economical state of oil and gas production enterprises has been developed (Table 3). There has been performed the pilot experiment, based on the results of which there was evaluated the risk factor impact on the resultant value. According to the results of the k -factors experiment, there have been defined $w = 2^k$ of possible combinations of risk factors. Matrices of possible combinations of risk factors for 6-, 5- and 3-factors experiments are represented in Table 3.

TABLE 3. MATRICES OF POSSIBLE COMBINATIONS OF RISK FACTORS
FOR K-FACTORS EXPERIMENT

Type of experiment			Risk factor (q_i)							
			Risk event (P_w)	q_1	q_2	q_3	q_4	q_5	q_6	y_w
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
2 ³ Full factorial experiment		P_1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	y_1
		P_2	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	y_2
		P_3	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	y_3
		P_4	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	y_4
		P_5	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	y_5
		P_6	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	y_6
		P_7	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	y_7
		P_8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	y_8
		P_9	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	y_9
		P_{10}	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	y_{10}
2 ⁵ Full factorial experiment		P_{11}	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	y_{11}
		P_{12}	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	y_{12}
		P_{13}	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	y_{13}
		P_{14}	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	y_{14}
		P_{15}	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	y_{15}
		P_{16}	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	y_{16}
		P_{17}	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	y_{17}
		P_{18}	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	y_{18}
		P_{19}	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	y_{19}
		P_{20}	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	y_{20}
		P_{21}	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	y_{21}

TABLE 3. MATRICES OF POSSIBLE COMBINATIONS OF RISK FACTORS FOR K-FACTORS EXPERIMENT

Type of experiment	Risk factor (q_i)							y_w
	Risk event (P_w)	q_1	q_2	q_3	q_4	q_5	q_6	
	P_{22}	1	0	0	1	1	0	y_{22}
	P_{23}	0	1	1	1	0	0	y_{23}
	P_{24}	0	1	1	0	1	0	y_{24}
	P_{25}	0	1	0	1	1	0	y_{25}
	P_{26}	0	0	1	1	1	0	y_{26}
	P_{27}	1	1	1	1	0	0	y_{27}
	P_{28}	0	1	1	1	1	0	y_{28}
	P_{29}	1	0	1	1	1	0	y_{29}
	P_{30}	1	1	0	1	1	0	y_{30}
	P_{31}	1	1	1	0	1	0	y_{31}
	P_{32}	1	1	1	1	1	0	y_{32}
	P_{33}	0	0	0	0	0	1	y_{33}
	P_{34}	1	0	0	0	0	1	y_{34}
	P_{35}	0	1	0	0	0	1	y_{35}
	P_{36}	0	0	1	0	0	1	y_{36}
	P_{37}	0	0	0	0	1	1	y_{37}
	P_{38}	0	0	0	1	0	1	y_{38}
	P_{39}	1	1	0	0	0	1	y_{39}
	P_{40}	1	0	1	0	0	1	y_{40}
	P_{41}	1	0	0	1	0	1	y_{41}
	P_{42}	1	0	0	0	1	1	y_{42}
	P_{43}	0	1	1	0	0	1	y_{43}
	P_{44}	0	1	0	1	0	1	y_{44}
	P_{45}	0	1	0	0	1	1	y_{45}
	P_{46}	0	0	1	1	0	1	y_{46}
	P_{47}	0	0	0	1	1	1	y_{47}
	P_{48}	1	1	1	0	0	1	y_{48}
	P_{49}	1	1	0	1	0	1	y_{49}
	P_{50}	1	1	0	0	1	1	y_{50}
	P_{51}	1	0	1	1	0	1	y_{51}
	P_{52}	1	0	1	0	1	1	y_{52}
	P_{53}	1	0	0	1	1	1	y_{53}
	P_{54}	0	1	1	1	0	1	y_{54}
	P_{55}	0	1	1	0	1	1	y_{55}
	P_{56}	0	1	0	1	1	1	y_{56}
	P_{57}	0	0	1	1	1	1	y_{57}
	P_{58}	1	1	1	1	0	1	y_{58}
	P_{59}	1	1	1	0	1	1	y_{59}
	P_{60}	1	1	0	1	1	1	y_{60}
	P_{61}	1	0	1	1	1	1	y_{61}
	P_{62}	0	1	1	1	1	1	y_{62}
	P_{63}	1	1	1	1	1	1	y_{63}
	P_{64}	0	0	1	0	1	1	y_{64}

Source: Author's development based on Doroshenko (1993).

2⁶ Full factorial experiment

Such number of combinations is caused by the direction of risk management system selected by the enterprise for each risk group investigated and its factors. Table 3 shows potential risk events (P_w) and respective values of its negative impact on the

financial and economical state of oil and gas production enterprises (y_w), where w is possible risk event number (for 6-factors experiment, it is equal to 64). y_w represents the risk magnitude in the context of non-performance of actions, aimed at the decrease of negative impact of certain $i_{neg.ef.}$ risk factors ($i = 1...k$) and in case of availability of positive impact of application of risk management techniques for neutralizing of possible losses, caused by $i_{pos.ef.}$ factors. In this case,

$$k_{neg.ef.} + k_{pos.ef.} = k, \quad (3)$$

Where, $k_{neg.ef.}$ is the number of factors whose negative impact isn't neutralized by risk management system, $k_{pos.ef.}$ is the number of factors whose negative impact is neutralized.

Thus, $i_{neg.ef.}$ risk factors are those, for which the level of risk neutralization is insignificant, i.e. those risk factors which may lead to possible negative results in case of P_w risk event; and $i_{pos.ef.}$ risk factors are those which negative impact has been neutralized by risk management system. Table 3 shows two types on risk level: 1 - for $i_{neg.ef.}$ risk factors and 0 - for $i_{pos.ef.}$ risk factors. So, basically, we have considered two situations:

- 1) if the negative impact is not reduced, when the value of risk level is denoted by "1" in Table 3;
- 2) if the negative impact is reduced, when the value of risk level is denoted by "0" in Table 3.

For example, negative impact of first, fourth and sixth factors hasn't been reduced against y_{41} of risk event P_{41} , but the negative impact of second, third and fifth risk factors has been reduced. The value of negative impact on the financial and economical state of oil and gas production enterprises (y_{41}) is equal to the sum of r_1 , r_4 and r_6 values of relevant q_1 , q_4 , and q_6 risk factors.

5. Results and discussion

Based on the matrices of possible combinations of k -factors experiments, which are represented in Table 3, y_w values of every possible risk event (P_w) of risk factors group (subgroup) are calculated as aforementioned. Table 4 shows, based on the y_w values, the risk events (P_w), ranked against its negative impact on the financial and economical state of oil and gas production enterprises for each group (subgroup) of risk factors.

Obtained results of risk events ranking against group of economic risk factors are represented graphically in Figure 1. Represented linear accumulative chart shows the overall and partial negative impact of factors (from 1 to 0) on the financial and economical state of oil and gas production enterprises for every risk event analyzed.

Let's simple average the high values (1) and the low (0) values in order to determine the difference or contrast. Mathematically, the calculation of an effect is expressed as follows:

$$Effect = \frac{\sum y_1}{s_{neg.ef.}} - \frac{\sum y_0}{s_{pos.ef.}}, \quad (4)$$

Where, the "s"s refer to the number of data points, have been collected at each level. The "y"s refer to the associated responses. We have picked these values from the matrices. For q_1 (three-factor experiments), the effect is:

$$Effect_{q_1} = \frac{y_1+y_4+y_5+y_7}{4} - \frac{y_2+y_3+y_6+y_8}{4}, \quad (5)$$

Results of the calculations, previously made, are represented in Table 5.

TABLE 5. DETERMINATION OF QI EFFECTS FOR ALL FACTORS

Effects of	Groups (subgroup) of risk factors						
	I group		II group	III group	IV group	V group	VI group
	1.3-1.8 Factors	1.2.1- 1.2.6 Factors					
q_1	0.101911	0.338696	0.336781	0.346095	0.036816	0.594930	0.065470
q_2	0.178960	0.040633	0.057013	0.604390	0.018159	0.238489	0.433969
q_3	0.252722	0.228525	0.021191	0.049515	0.006219	0.166580	0.276842
q_4	0.009862	0.293973	0.102170	-	0.130348	-	0.201646
q_5	0.437436	0.025907	0.009839	-	0.409204	-	0.022073
q_6	0.019108	0.072266	0.473007	-	0.399254	-	-

Source: Own.

We use a 5% (0.05) significance level in our research. So, if the risk factor negative impact on the financial and economical state of oil and gas production enterprises is less when 5% (0.05), we have to exclude (screen) that factor at the stage of model construction. In comparison to the overall spread of results, it seems that the following factors have very little effect on financial and economical state of oil and gas production enterprises; among them are: 1) low-quality protection against lightning, possibility of equipment self-ignition (4.3 factor in Table 1, see Appendix); 2) inefficient staff retraining system (2.5 factor); 3) defects in equipment repair and maintenance system (1.6 factor); 4) the considerable density of equipment location on the territory of the production site - domino effect (4.2 factor); 5) modification of techniques and production conditions of well stock as the result of field development closing stage (1.8 factor); 6) inappropriate skill level of management, engineering and operational personnel (factor 2.3); 7) Sputnik automatic pad metering station - saline deposit (1.2.5 factor); 8) low level of expenses connected with increase of "environmental friendliness of production" (4.1 factor); 9) breakdowns of plunger oil-well sucker-rod pump due to paraffin deposit (1.2.2 factor); 10) irrelevance of information (3.2.3 factor); 11) low cost and availability of alternative sources of energy. The impact (or "negative effect") of other factors are much larger than that of above-listed factors.

6. Limitation of study

Although the research has reached its aims, there were some unavoidable limitations.

The risk magnitude of risk factors (risk index) was calculated purely based on experts' judgment. Therefore, the accuracy level of the conducted risk assessment is not as high as it could be.

Among other things, experimental research creates artificial situations that partially don't represent real-life situations. This is largely due to fact that all risk factors can be volatile between 0 and 1. However, in our simulation experiment, each factor had only two levels (a low - "0" and a high - "1"). The negative impact of a particular risk factor can be reduced in real-life situations, and the value of risk level will come within a range of 0 to 1.

7. Conclusion

As a result of the research performed, we may reveal the following outcomes. There are some difficulties of oil and gas production enterprises management in terms of conducting business by it under the conditions of risk and uncertainty. The lack of complex experimental studies of special risks of domestic oil and gas companies has determined necessity for coordinated expert estimation of such risk factors in our earlier academic papers. Doing a screening design is useful when a higher level or a more complex design may be required at a later stage. In order to construct the adequate model of assessment of risk of oil and gas production enterprises activity, developed on the basis of fuzzy logic, it has been suggested to exclude (screen) at the stage of model construction eleven risk factors (of thirty-five ones identified), which impact on the financial and economical state of analyzed companies is insignificant (less than 5%).

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Appendix

TABLE 1. SPECIFIC RISKS AND RISK FACTORS OF OIL AND GAS PRODUCTION ENTERPRISES

No of risk group	RISK GROUP	RISK FACTORS
1	2	3
1	Production and technological risk	1.2. Machinery breakdowns by the causes of its occurrence: 1.2.1 Underground equipment (plunger oil-well sucker-rod pump) - sucker rod; 1.2.2. Underground equipment (plunger oil-well sucker-rod pump) - paraffin deposit; 1.2.3. Underground equipment (plunger oil-well sucker-rod pump, electric submersible pump) - imperfect design; 1.2.4. Underground equipment (plunger oil-well sucker-rod pump, electric submersible pump) - distortion; 1.2.5. Sputnik automatic pad metering station - saline deposit; 1.2.6. Crude oil pipeline leakage, loss of containment - internal corrosion. 1.3. Insufficient level of technologies 1.4. Equipment obsolescence 1.5. High level of depreciation of equipment 1.6. Defects in equipment repair and maintenance system 1.7. Substantial quantity of depleted reserves and reserves difficult to be recovered 1.8. Modification of techniques and production conditions of well stock as the result of field development closing stage
2	Human as a risk factor	2.1. Non-compliance with standards and technical documentation as to the industrial machinery operations 2.2. Inefficient functioning of work safety service and occupational safety 2.3. Inappropriate skill level of management, engineering and operational personnel 2.4. Incompetency of heads of production and non-production departments 2.5. Inefficient staff retraining system 2.6. Inefficient employee incentive system
3	Information risk	3.2. Inefficient automatic control system: 3.2.1. Time required for preparation of necessary information; 3.2.2. Time lag of obtainment of necessary information; 3.2.3. Irrelevance of information
4	Environmental risk	4.1. Low level of expenses connected with increase of "environmental friendliness of production" 4.2. The considerable density of equipment location on the territory of the production site - domino effect 4.3. Low-quality lightning-discharge protection, possibility of equipment self-ignition 4.4. Violation of parameters of technological processes performance 4.5. Essential man-induced impact on environment 4.6. Absence of scientific-based environmental risk management system at oil and gas production enterprises
5	Geological risk	5.1. The actual geological and physical properties of the productive formations differ from the predicted ones (not confirmed numerical characteristics of deposits)

TABLE 1. SPECIFIC RISKS AND RISK FACTORS OF OIL AND GAS PRODUCTION ENTERPRISES

No of risk group	RISK GROUP	RISK FACTORS
1	2	3
6	Economic risk	5.2. The risk of loss caused by inaccurate determination of reserves and oil recovery factor of the deposits
		5.3. Mistakes during the reservoir and production engineering (equipment, operation conditions, etc.)
		6.1. Cutting of oil and gas prices
		6.2. Unstable tax legislation concerning subsoil users
		6.3. Non-differentiation of fee rate for use of mineral resources depending on oil extraction conditions
		6.4. Unsatisfactory investment climate in Ukraine
		6.5. Low cost and availability of alternative sources of energy

Source: Gryniuk (2016b).

TABLE 4. RANKING OF RISK EVENTS BASED ON ITS NEGATIVE IMPACT ON THE FINANCIAL AND ECONOMICAL STATE OF OIL AND GAS PRODUCTION ENTERPRISES FOR GROUPS (SUBGROUPS) OF RISK FACTORS

No.	1. Factors of production and technological risk				2. Human as a risk factor		3. Information risk factors		4. Environmental risk factor		5. Geological risk factors		6. Economic risk factors				
	1.3-1.8 Factors (see tab.1)		1.2.1- 1.2.6 Factors of 1.2 Subgroup		P_w	y_w	P_w	y_w	P_w	y_w	P_w	y_w	P_w	y_w			
	P_w	y_w	P_w	y_w											2	3	4
1	P_{63}	1.0000	P_{63}	1.0000	P_{63}	1.0000	P_7	1.0000	P_{63}	1.0000	P_7	1.0000	P_{32}	1.0000			
2	P_{59}	0.9901	P_{58}	0.9741	P_{58}	0.9902	P_4	0.9505	P_{60}	0.9938	P_4	0.8334	P_{27}	0.9779			
3	P_{32}	0.9809	P_{61}	0.9594	P_{60}	0.9788	P_6	0.6539	P_{61}	0.9818	P_5	0.7615	P_{28}	0.9345			
4	P_{31}	0.9710	P_{51}	0.9335	P_{49}	0.9690	P_2	0.6044	P_{53}	0.9756	P_1	0.5949	P_{23}	0.9125			
5	P_{62}	0.8981	P_{32}	0.9277	P_{61}	0.9430	P_5	0.3956	P_{62}	0.9632	P_6	0.4051	P_{31}	0.7984			
6	P_{55}	0.8882	P_{27}	0.9018	P_{51}	0.9331	P_1	0.3461	P_{56}	0.9570	P_2	0.2385	P_7	0.7763			
7	P_{28}	0.8790	P_{29}	0.8871	P_{53}	0.9218	P_3	0.0495	P_{57}	0.9450	P_3	0.1666	P_{24}	0.7329			
8	P_{24}	0.8691	P_{20}	0.8612	P_{41}	0.9120	P_8	0.0000	P_{47}	0.9388	P_8	0.0000	P_{30}	0.7232			
9	P_{61}	0.8210	P_{60}	0.7715	P_{59}	0.8978			P_{59}	0.8697			P_6	0.7108			
10	P_{52}	0.8112	P_{49}	0.7456	P_{48}	0.8880			P_{50}	0.8634			P_{18}	0.7011			
11	P_{29}	0.8019	P_{53}	0.7308	P_{50}	0.8766			P_{52}	0.8515			P_{25}	0.6577			
12	P_{21}	0.7921	P_{59}	0.7060	P_{39}	0.8668			P_{42}	0.8453			P_{13}	0.6356			
13	P_{60}	0.7473	P_{41}	0.7049	P_{52}	0.8408			P_{55}	0.8328			P_{29}	0.5660			
14	P_{50}	0.7374	P_{30}	0.6992	P_{40}	0.8310			P_{45}	0.8266			P_{20}	0.5440			
15	P_{30}	0.7282	P_{48}	0.6801	P_{42}	0.8196			P_{64}	0.8147			P_{19}	0.5215			
16	P_{57}	0.7191	P_{18}	0.6733	P_{34}	0.8098			P_{37}	0.8085			P_{26}	0.5006			
17	P_{19}	0.7183	P_{52}	0.6654	P_{62}	0.6632			P_{32}	0.6007			P_4	0.4994			
18	P_{64}	0.7093	P_{62}	0.6613	P_{54}	0.6534			P_{30}	0.5945			P_{15}	0.4785			
19	P_{26}	0.7000	P_{22}	0.6586	P_{56}	0.6420			P_{58}	0.5908			P_{14}	0.4560			
20	P_{16}	0.6902	P_{40}	0.6395	P_{44}	0.6322			P_{49}	0.5846			P_2	0.4340			
21	P_{56}	0.6454	P_{54}	0.6354	P_{57}	0.6062			P_{29}	0.5826			P_{21}	0.3644			
22	P_{45}	0.6355	P_{31}	0.6338	P_{46}	0.5964			P_{22}	0.5764			P_5	0.3423			
23	P_{25}	0.6263	P_{11}	0.6327	P_{47}	0.5850			P_{51}	0.5726			P_{16}	0.2989			

TABLE 4. RANKING OF RISK EVENTS BASED ON ITS NEGATIVE IMPACT ON THE FINANCIAL AND ECONOMICAL STATE OF OIL AND GAS PRODUCTION ENTERPRISES FOR GROUPS (SUBGROUPS) OF RISK FACTORS

No.	1. Factors of production and technological risk				2. Human as a risk factor		3. Information risk factors		4. Environmental risk factor		5. Geological risk factors		6. Economic risk factors	
	1.3-1.8 Factors (see tab.1)		1.2.1- 1.2.6 Factors of 1.2 Subgroup		P_w	y_w	P_w	y_w	P_w	y_w	P_w	y_w	P_w	y_w
	2	3	4	5										
24	P_{14}	0.6164	P_{57}	0.6207	P_{38}	0.5752			P_{41}	0.5664			P_{22}	0.2892
25	P_{53}	0.5683	P_7	0.6079	P_{55}	0.5611			P_{28}	0.5639			P_3	0.2768
26	P_{58}	0.5626	P_{46}	0.5948	P_{43}	0.5512			P_{25}	0.5577			P_{11}	0.2671
27	P_{42}	0.5585	P_{21}	0.5931	P_{45}	0.5399			P_{54}	0.5540			P_{17}	0.2237
28	P_{48}	0.5527	P_{28}	0.5890	P_{35}	0.5300			P_{44}	0.5478			P_9	0.2016
29	P_{22}	0.5492	P_5	0.5672	P_{32}	0.5270			P_{26}	0.5458			P_{12}	0.0875
30	P_{27}	0.5435	P_{23}	0.5631	P_{27}	0.5172			P_{17}	0.5396			P_1	0.0655
31	P_{12}	0.5393	P_{26}	0.5484	P_{30}	0.5058			P_{46}	0.5358			P_{10}	0.0221
32	P_7	0.5336	P_{15}	0.5225	P_{64}	0.5040			P_{38}	0.5296			P_8	0.0000
33	P_{47}	0.4664	P_{50}	0.4775	P_{18}	0.4960			P_{31}	0.4704				
34	P_{54}	0.4607	P_{39}	0.4516	P_{36}	0.4942			P_{19}	0.4642				
35	P_{37}	0.4565	P_{42}	0.4369	P_{37}	0.4828			P_{48}	0.4604				
36	P_{43}	0.4508	P_{56}	0.4328	P_{33}	0.4730			P_{39}	0.4542				
37	P_{17}	0.4473	P_{34}	0.4110	P_{29}	0.4700			P_{21}	0.4522				
38	P_{23}	0.4415	P_{44}	0.4069	P_{20}	0.4601			P_{12}	0.4460				
39	P_{10}	0.4374	P_{19}	0.4052	P_{22}	0.4488			P_{40}	0.4423				
40	P_6	0.4317	P_{47}	0.3921	P_{11}	0.4390			P_{34}	0.4361				
41	P_{51}	0.3836	P_4	0.3793	P_{31}	0.4248			P_{24}	0.4336				
42	P_{40}	0.3737	P_{55}	0.3673	P_7	0.4150			P_{14}	0.4274				
43	P_{20}	0.3645	P_{38}	0.3662	P_{19}	0.4036			P_{43}	0.4236				
44	P_5	0.3546	P_{12}	0.3646	P_4	0.3938			P_{35}	0.4174				
45	P_{49}	0.3098	P_{25}	0.3605	P_{21}	0.3678			P_{16}	0.4154				
46	P_{39}	0.3000	P_{43}	0.3414	P_5	0.3580			P_{10}	0.4092				
47	P_{18}	0.2907	P_1	0.3387	P_{12}	0.3466			P_{36}	0.4055				
48	P_{46}	0.2817	P_{13}	0.3346	P_1	0.3368			P_{33}	0.3993				
49	P_4	0.2809	P_{64}	0.3267	P_{28}	0.1902			P_{27}	0.1915				
50	P_{36}	0.2718	P_{17}	0.3199	P_{23}	0.1804			P_{18}	0.1853				
51	P_{15}	0.2626	P_{36}	0.3008	P_{25}	0.1690			P_{20}	0.1734				
52	P_3	0.2527	P_{24}	0.2951	P_{13}	0.1592			P_{11}	0.1672				
53	P_{44}	0.2079	P_9	0.2940	P_{26}	0.1332			P_{23}	0.1547				
54	P_{35}	0.1981	P_6	0.2692	P_{15}	0.1234			P_{13}	0.1485				
55	P_{13}	0.1888	P_{16}	0.2544	P_{17}	0.1120			P_{15}	0.1366				
56	P_2	0.1790	P_3	0.2285	P_9	0.1022			P_9	0.1303				
57	P_{41}	0.1309	P_{45}	0.1388	P_{24}	0.0880			P_7	0.0612				
58	P_{34}	0.1210	P_{35}	0.1129	P_6	0.0782			P_4	0.0550				
59	P_{11}	0.1118	P_{37}	0.0982	P_{14}	0.0669			P_5	0.0430				
60	P_1	0.1019	P_{33}	0.0723	P_2	0.0570			P_1	0.0368				
61	P_{38}	0.0290	P_{14}	0.0665	P_{16}	0.0310			P_6	0.0244				
62	P_{33}	0.0191	P_2	0.0406	P_3	0.0212			P_2	0.0182				
63	P_9	0.0099	P_{10}	0.0259	P_{10}	0.0098			P_3	0.0062				
64	P_8	0.0000	P_8	0.0000	P_8	0.0000			P_8	0.0000				

Source: Developed by the Author based on pilot experiment.

FIGURE 1. RESULTS OF RISK EVENTS RANKING BASED ON ITS NEGATIVE IMPACT ON THE FINANCIAL AND ECONOMICAL STATE OF OIL AND GAS PRODUCTION ENTERPRISES FOR SIXTH GROUP OF RISK FACTORS (ECONOMIC RISK FACTORS)

Source: Own.